

UNBOXING THE IMPACT OF GREEN PRODUCT ORIENTATION AND SOCIAL INFLUENCE ON GREEN PRODUCT PURCHASE INTENTIONS: A MODERATING CASE OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERN.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17159254>

Keywords

Social Influence, Green
Product Orientation,
Environmental Concerns.

Article History

Received on 18 Aug 2025

Accepted on 28 Aug 2025

Published on 19 Sep 2025

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Abstract

This research examines the factors influencing consumer intentions to purchase green products in Pakistan, specifically focusing on social influences, green product orientation. The study also explores the moderating effect of environmental concerns between the variables. Data were collected from consumers aware of green products through a structured survey with a five-point Likert scale, using a descriptive research design and simple random sampling. The analysis, conducted using PLS-SEM (4.0). These findings suggest that businesses and policymakers should leverage social influence and align marketing strategies with consumer environmental values. Additionally, promoting social support for green initiatives and providing incentives could increase green product adoption rates. The future research is intended to investigate other moderating variables, to use longitudinal study designs, and to include other demographics to gain more insight into the factors driving green product purchase intentions.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has been a core issue in global studies since the Brundtland Commission report in 1987 and the Earth Summit in 1992 (Robert & Brown, 2004). Since then, it has become central in fields like environmental science, economics, and policy, sparking efforts to meet current needs without risking future generations' ability to do the same. Today, sustainability has shifted from a positive idea to a critical goal for businesses and organizations (Wu et al., 2020). Increased consumer spending over the last ten years has depleted natural resources and degraded the environment (Wu et al., 2020). Overpopulation and high consumption are key causes of continued environmental catastrophes, such as water and air pollution, global warming, biodiversity loss, and ozone depletion (X. Wang et al., 2021). Businesses have created green manufacturing and marketing strategies to fulfil the demands of their immediate consumers and future shareholders as consumer tastes alter and environmental challenges become more serious (Saha et al., 2023). This study looks deeply into the complicated web of influences influencing customers' proclivity to purchase eco-friendly things, revealing unexpected discoveries. This initiative revolves around "green product purchase intention," which defines people's proclivity to buy things with beneficial environmental benefits. This research aims to provide a comprehensive knowledge of the factors that encourage people to take environmentally responsible actions in a society afflicted by enormous environmental concerns.

Literature Review

Social Influence:

All of these, that is, individuals, communities, media, and the commercial sector, play an

important role in setting societal norms and trends and, thus, have an influence on consumer behavior as a whole. Social influence is the force behind changing people's opinions and beliefs regarding products due to social factors. Conformity, peer pressure, obedience, and marketing are the common ways through which social influence molds consumer attitudes toward environmental-friendly products (Hariyadi et al., 2021). Customers are more likely to make environmentally responsible purchases when they believe that "important others" approve of such actions. According to (Schwarzl, 2015), consumer expectations play a significant role in influencing people's views. Two recent studies came to a similar conclusion by acknowledging the influence of customers' views on the opinions of products held by their social group. There are a variety of social influences that might eventually convince consumers to change their habits and choose green products. These influences include social norms, peer pressure, and the desire to be seen as socially responsible (Dash, 2021).

H1: Social Influence has significantly impacts on Green Product Purchase Intention.

Green Product Orientation:

Green product orientation refers to a strong preference for non-harmful, all-natural items that are also good for the environment. Assumptions about a person's nature-loving tendencies are reinforced when they are associated with eco-friendly items (Cronin-gilmore, 2012). According to (Details, 2006), "orientation" is the process by which a company attempts to differentiate its

product or service from competitors by altering its overt and covert features. Important for influencing the opinions of target customers, a defined orientation strategy helps guarantee that aspects of the marketing program are consistent and helpful (Zhao et al., 2022). According to the findings, there is a positive and significant relationship between the dimensions of consumer orientation (social value orientation, social status orientation, social influence orientation, and man nature orientation) and the attitudes that lead to the intention to buy environmentally friendly products. As revealed by (Ibodov, 2021), green product orientation significantly affects customers' attitudes toward purchasing green products. According to research by (Liu et al., 2010), green product orientation correlates positively with green management attitudes. Based on the above-analyzed literature review, the developed hypotheses of the study are;

H2: Product Orientation has significantly impacts on Green Product Purchase Intention

Environmental Concern:

"Environmental concern" characterizes the degree to which individuals are concerned about environmental issues such as global warming, pollution, resource depletion, and extinction. It demonstrates that people care about the environment and are willing to take action to solve environmental problems (Coman et al., 2020). This

Research Framework

concern also plays a crucial role in shaping public opinion and influencing policy decisions that aim to protect and preserve the environment for future generations. As the country struggles with water scarcity, air pollution, and deforestation, many Pakistanis recognize the need to address environmental issues. According to (Andika et al., 2021), Concern for the environment correlates significantly with the propensity to purchase eco-friendly products. Those who prioritize environmental protection are more likely to purchase green products. As environmental concerns grow in the future, our culture is under increasing pressure to shift towards "green" consumerism. This study (Chauhan et al., 2021) looked into what makes people more likely to buy eco-friendly goods online. To put this theory to the test, researcher surveyed 182 buyers and employed the partial least squares technique. The findings highlight the importance of social influence and perceived utility in influencing customers' decisions to buy green products online.

H3: Environmental Concern significantly moderates the relationship between Social Influence and Green Product Purchase Intention.

H4: Environmental Concern significantly moderates the relationship between Green Product Orientation and Green Product Purchase Intention.

Research Design

Because the primary goal was to investigate the effects of the variables proposed to influence the intention to purchase green products, this study is a quantitative research design that seeks to explain correlations between variables. The current study will examine how environmental concerns influence the relationship between green product purchase intention and social influence, green product orientation. This study used a descriptive research approach to test the hypotheses and determine the actual relationship between the dependent variable (intention to buy green products) and the independent variables (social influence, green product orientation). That is why environmental concerns act as a moderator. The

current study used PLS-SEM and other statistical methodologies to evaluate and investigate the correlations between variables in the population (Awang, 2012; Sekaran, 2007). The target population of the present study refers to the individuals willing to buy green products in Pakistan. However, the sampling frame refers to the cities of south Punjab, specifically Multan, Bahawalpur. Sampling in quantitative research aims to obtain data from a representative sample of the population. According to Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) generalized scientific criteria for sample size decisions, this study's optimal number of participants is 351. According to Kumar et al. (2013), the current study's assumptions and objectives influenced the decision to utilize a questionnaire as a data collection tool.

Results and Finding

Descriptive statistics:

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..1 Descriptive Analysis

Item	Type	Mean	Median	Scale min	Scale max	Standard deviation	Excess kurtosis	Skewness
GPPI1	ORD	3.745	4	1	5	0.739	1.177	-0.608
GPPI2	ORD	3.779	4	1	5	0.727	1.305	-0.582
GPPI3	ORD	3.789	4	1	5	0.649	-0.306	0.019
GPPI4	ORD	3.295	3	1	5	0.901	-0.881	0.046
SI1	ORD	3.728	4	1	5	0.845	1.704	-0.956
SI2	ORD	3.164	3	1	5	0.957	-0.888	0.127
SI3	ORD	3.725	4	1	5	0.822	1.996	-0.98
SI4	ORD	3.765	4	1	5	0.772	2.012	-0.887
GPO1	ORD	3.758	4	1	5	0.706	1.313	-0.48
GPO2	ORD	3.785	4	1	5	0.681	1.589	-0.469
GPO3	ORD	3.614	4	1	5	0.924	-0.59	-0.594
GPO4	ORD	3.768	4	1	5	0.673	-0.175	-0.083
EC1	ORD	3.762	4	1	5	0.819	1.993	-1.005
EC2	ORD	3.19	3	1	5	0.928	-0.835	0.117
EC3	ORD	3.742	4	1	5	0.801	2.15	-0.996
EC4	ORD	3.772	4	1	5	0.734	1.594	-0.637

Convergent Reliability and Validity

The primary objective of a convergent validity analysis is to determine the reliability and validity of the research scale items.

Convergent Reliability

Constructs	Items	Factor Loading	CA	CR	AVE
Environmental Concern	EC1	0.811	0.766	0.852	0.599
	EC2	0.533			
	EC3	0.896			
	EC4	0.805			
Green Product Orientation	GPO1	0.881	0.835	0.894	0.684
	GPO2	0.919			
	GPO3	0.571			
	GPO4	0.888			
Green Product Purchase Intention	GPPI1	0.852	0.824	0.885	0.664
	GPPI2	0.892			

	GPPI3	0.904			
	GPPI4	0.563			
	SI1	0.799	0.762	0.851	0.592
Social Influence	SI2	0.620			
	SI3	0.884			
	SI4	0.750			

Cross Loading:

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..2 Cross Loading

	EC	GPO	GPPI	SI
EC1	0.811	0.797	0.740	0.788
EC2	0.533	0.417	0.400	0.569
EC3	0.896	0.776	0.765	0.876
EC4	0.805	0.719	0.804	0.776
GPO1	0.750	0.881	0.873	0.746
GPO2	0.879	0.919	0.880	0.884
GPO3	0.372	0.571	0.382	0.381
GPO4	0.874	0.888	0.887	0.861
GPPI1	0.774	0.814	0.852	0.779
GPPI2	0.817	0.873	0.892	0.805
GPPI3	0.839	0.867	0.904	0.828
GPPI4	0.421	0.422	0.563	0.419
SI2	0.559	0.456	0.427	0.620
SI3	0.884	0.769	0.761	0.884
SI4	0.753	0.677	0.763	0.750

Direct Relationship

Direct Relationship

	Beta	Standard	T	P	Remar
	Coefficient	deviation	statistics	values	ks
SI -> GPPI	0.522	0.094	5.526	0.00	Supported
GPO -> GPPI	0.464	0.126	3.692	0.00	Supported

As per finding of current research social influence has significant impact on green product purchase intention and the finding of this research is aligned with previous researches (Rathnayaka & Gunawardana, 2021; Singh et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2020). Additionally, green product orientation has

significant impact on green product purchase intention and the finding of this research is aligned with previous researches (Chauhan et al.,

2021; Chi, 2021; Liang et al., 2021; Pop et al., 2020; Rathnayaka & Gunawardana, 2021; Zhuang et al., 2021).

Moderations Effect

Moderating Effect

	Beta Coefficient	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values	Remarks
EC x SI -> GPPI	0.503	0.629	0.800	0.230	Not Support
EC x GPO -> GPPI	0.244	0.091	2.681	0.001	Support

Environmental concern only has a non-significant moderating effect on social influence and intention to buy green products. The relationship between green product orientation and intention to buy green products is, however, accepted to be significantly moderated by environmental concern

Conclusion

In general, findings were able to explain how the social determinants of social norms, peer influence and collective action affect purchase intention toward the green product. The social determinant: social norm works by creating an expectation in terms of doing something in an eco-friendly manner thus influencing purchasing adjustment through the social identity in sustaining the green purchasing behavior through common values held by people in a close network that makes influencers to be good marketers for green product. Green product orientation has a positive effect on pro-environmental behavior, as it increases awareness and reinforces social norms to decrease cognitive dissonance in support of environmental values. Environmentally oriented consumers are influenced more by the perceived advantages that green products offer them rather than by the values shared by companies that use more sustainable practices. This study contributes

to the literature because it shows how environmental concern strengthens the links between green product orientation, Social influence with purchase intention. These specific relationships can thus be highlighted to be used by businesses and policymakers in campaigns appealing directly to consumers' environmental values and motivations.

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